

Supplemental Information

Intestinal epithelial NAD⁺ biosynthesis regulates GLP-1 production and postprandial glucose metabolism in mice

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Figure S1

Figure S1. *Villin*-Cre transgenic mice have similar *Nampt* expression, NAD⁺ levels, and *Proglucagon* to fl/fl mice

(a) *Nampt* expression in whole extracts of jejunum, ileum, and colon measured in 2- to 5-month-old *Villin*-Cre transgenic (Cre) and control (fl/fl) male mice (n = 3–9 per group). (b) Tissue NAD⁺ levels in whole extracts of jejunum, ileum, and colon from 3- to 4-month-old fl/fl and *Villin*-Cre transgenic (Cre) male mice (n = 4 per group). (c) Ileal gene expression of *Proglucagon* in 2- to 5-month-old Cre and fl/fl male mice (n = 3–5 per group). Data were analyzed using Student's unpaired *t*-test, and are presented as mean ± SEM.

Figure S2

Figure S2. Deletion of *Nampt* decreases NAD⁺ levels and disrupts intestinal architecture in the colon

(a) *Nampt* expression in whole colon extracts of 2- to 4-month-old fl/fl and INKO male mice (n = 6–7 per group). (b) Western blot and quantification of NAMPT and β -ACTIN in whole colon extracts from 3- to 5-month-old fl/fl and INKO male mice (n = 4 per group). (c) Tissue NAD⁺ levels in whole colon extracts from 4-7-month-old fl/fl and INKO male mice (n = 5–6 per group). (d) Colon lengths in 2- to 5-month-old male mice (n = 6–7 per group). (e) Representative images of Masson trichrome-stained longitudinal colon sections from 2- to 6-month-old fl/fl and INKO male mice (Scale bar, 50 μ m). (f) Quantification of colon submucosal fibrous layer thickness in 2- to 6-month-old fl/fl and INKO male mice (n = 3 per group). (g) Expression of fibrosis marker genes in colon determined by real-time PCR in 2- to 5-month-old male INKO and fl/fl mice (n = 4–5 per group). *aSMA*, smooth-muscle actin. Data were analyzed using Student's unpaired *t*-test, and are presented as means \pm SEM. **p* < 0.05.

Figure S3

Figure S3. Intestinal epithelial cell-specific *Nampt* deletion has minimal impact on energy metabolism

Characterization of energy metabolism in fl/fl and INKO male mice fed with RCD. (a) Body weights of male mice monitored from 6 to 11 weeks (n = 7–8 per group). There was a significant time effect ($p < 0.05$) but no group x time interaction (ANOVA). (b) Daily food intakes of individually-housed male mice (n = 3 per group). (c) Energy expenditure over the light and dark cycle determined by indirect calorimetry in 4- to 7-month-old males (n= 5 per group). White shading indicates the light period and gray shading indicates the dark period. Data were analyzed using Student's unpaired *t*-test, and are presented as mean \pm SEM.

Figure S4. *Nampt* deletion in intestinal epithelial cells impairs oral glucose tolerance in female mice

Metabolic parameters in 2- to 6-month-old female INKO and control (fl/fl) mice fed regular chow. (a)

Body weights of female mice monitored from 6 to 11 weeks (n = 5 per group). There was a significant time effect ($P < 0.05$) but no group x time interaction (ANOVA). (b-c) Whole-body glucose metabolism in female INKO and fl/fl mice. (b) Intraperitoneal glucose tolerance tests (IPGTTs) (n = 5-10 per group) and (c) oral glucose tolerance tests (OGTTs) (n = 6-8 per group). Area under the curve (AUC) for glucose is shown next to each curve. Data were analyzed by the Student's unpaired t test, and are presented as mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

Figure S5

Figure S5. *Nampt* deletion in intestinal epithelial cells has minimal impact on expression of glucose transporter genes

Gene expression of glucose transporters in the small intestine was determined by real-time PCR in 2- to 5-month-old male INKO and fl/fl mice (n = 4 per group). *Sglt1*; sodium/glucose cotransporter 1, *Glut5*; facilitated glucose transporter 5, *Glut2*; facilitated glucose transporter 2. Data were analyzed using Student's unpaired *t*-test, and are presented as means \pm SEM.

(a)

(b)

Figure S6. Effect of NAD⁺ biosynthesis in intestines on jejunal *Gip* expression

(a) Jejunum *Gip* mRNA expression in 2- to 5-month-old male INKO and fl/fl mice (n = 4-5 per group). (b)

Jejunum *Gip* mRNA expression in 4- to 5-week-old NMN-treated (gray bar) and NMN-untreated INKO

(black bar) mice (n = 3 per group). NMN (500 mg/kg-body weight/day) or water was administered to male

INKO mice by oral gavage for 7 consecutive days soon after weaning at 3 to 4 weeks of age. Data were

analyzed using Student's unpaired *t*-test, and are presented as mean ± SEM.

Table S1

Sequence of primers for real-time PCR

Gene	Accession Number	Forward Primer (5'→3')	Reverse Primer (5'→3')
<i>18S rRNA</i>	NM_011296	TTCTGGCCAACGGTCTAGACAAC	CCAGTGGTCTTGGTGTGCTGA
<i>Nampt</i>	NM_021524	GCAGAAGCCGAGTTCAACATC	TTTTCACGGCATTCAAAGTAGGA
<i>Proglucagon</i>	NM_008100	TTACTTTGTGGCTGGATTGCTT	AGTGGCGTTTGTCTTCATTCA
<i>Gip</i>	NM_008119	TGAGTTCCGATCCCATGCTAA	CCAGTTCACGAAGTCTTGTGTC
<i>Lgr5</i>	NM_010195	CCTACTCGAAGACTTACCCAGT	GCATTGGGGTGAATGATAGCA
<i>Axin2</i>	NM_015732	TGACTCTCCTTCCAGATCCCA	TGCCCACACTAGGCTGACA
<i>βcatenin</i>	NM_001165902	ATGGAGCCGGACAGAAAAGC	CTTGCCACTCAGGGAAGGA
<i>Wnt3</i>	NM_009521	CTCGCTGGCTACCCAATTTG	CTTCACACCTTCTGCTACGCT
<i>Sglt1</i>	NM_019810	ATGCGGCTGACATCTCAGTC	ACCAAGGCGTTCCATTCAAAG
<i>Glut5</i>	NM_019741	CCAATATGGGTACAACGTAGCTG	GCGTCAAGGTGAAGGACTCAATA
<i>Glut2</i>	NM_031197	TCAGAAGACAAGATCACCGGA	GCTGGTGTGACTGTAAGTGGG
<i>αSMA</i>	NM_007392	GTCCCAGACATCAGGGAGTAA	TCGGATACTTCAGCGTCAGGA
<i>Fibronectin</i>	NM_010233	ATGTGGACCCCTCCTGATAGT	GCCCAGTGATTCAGCAAAGG

Table S1: Primers for real-time PCR